

Prevalence of *CDKN2A* gene deletion in Breast Cancer: An Indian experience

Kazi Mahnaz M.¹, Trivedi Pina J.^{2*}, Patel Dharmesh M.³, Varma Priya K.⁴

¹Junior Research Assistant, Cytogenetics Lab, Gujarat Cancer & Research Institute

²Senior Scientific Officer & Head, Cytogenetics Lab, Gujarat Cancer & Research Institute

³Research Assistant, Cytogenetics Lab, Gujarat Cancer & Research Institute

⁴Junior Research Fellow, Cytogenetics Lab, Gujarat Cancer & Research Institute

*Corresponding author

E-mail IDs: mahnaz.kazi@geriindia.org; pina.trivedi@geriindia.org; dharmesh.patel@geriindia.org,
priya.varma@geriindia.org

Abstract

Background:

Breast cancer is the most common cancer in females, found to be associated with mutations in various genes. *CDKN2A* is one such tumor suppressor gene which is altered in a wide range of human neoplasms and most frequently shown to play a role in breast cancer. It may be used in the development of a targeted therapy that could result in improved patient prognostication and outcome. In the present study the frequency of *CDKN2A* gene deletion and its relationship with clinicopathological features were examined in breast cancer patients.

Method: Histopathologically confirmed breast cancer patients were included for *CDKN2A* gene deletion study by Fluorescence *in situ* hybridization (FISH) method. Formalin fixed paraffin embedded tissues were used for the assays. A total of 30 breast cancer patients were included. FISH was performed using P16 (*CDKN2A*) deletion probe kit. Images were captured by Epi-fluorescence microscope.

Result: In breast cancer patients, *CDKN2A* gene was deleted in 22 patients (73%) with 17 hemizygous and 5 homozygous deletions, while 8 patients (27%) had normal intact form. *CDKN2A* gene deletion in breast cancer was found to be significantly inversely associated with tumor grade, presence of perineural invasion, perinodal extension and vascular permeation.

Summary and Conclusion: *CDKN2A* gene deletion was associated with absence of known worse prognosticators indicating that the gene expression and not loss was linked to adverse tumor parameters. Hence, detection of *CDKN2A* gene deletion could help to stratify the specific subsets of patients into high risk and low risk groups. *CDKN2A* gene deletion can also help as the pre-screening tool prior to gene evaluation tests.

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer has thrived to become the most common cancer representing 1 in 4 cancers diagnosed among women worldwide, according to Globocan 2020. Despite advances in oncology, breast cancer remains the leading cause of cancer deaths in female globally (Sung et al, 2021). It is, therefore, a prerequisite to define and understand events resulting in breast carcinogenesis at the molecular level. It has been detected that various chromosome are affected by a higher frequency of structural or numerical abnormalities in breast cancer. (Brenner and Aldaz, 1995). At the molecular level, several somatic mutations have also been described affecting various oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes. Such mutations in cell cycle-related genes such as *TP53*, *CDKN2A*, *RB1* and *BRCA1* usually lead to tumor formation.

CDKN2A gene localized at chromosome 9p21

encodes for p16 tumor suppressor protein that has been discussed as a prognostic factor in breast cancer. It inhibits cyclin-dependent kinases (CDKs) 4 and 6 at the G₁ to S-phase transition of the cell cycle and thus prevents phosphorylation of the retinoblastoma (RB1) protein (Sherr et al, 2004). Maintaining hypophosphorylation of RB family members promotes binding to E2F1 and leads to G₁ cell cycle arrest (Li et al, 2011). Owing to this, p16 is fundamental in various tumor types including colon cancer, melanoma and gallbladder (Romagosa et al, 2011). Moreover, a vital role of p16 expression is suggested in breast cancer for tumor progression (Milde-Langosch et al, 2001; Witkiewicz et al, 2011; Karray-Chouayekh et al, 2011; Hui et al, 2000), metastasis (Hui et al, 2000), and clinical outcome (Karray-Chouayekh et al, 2011; Hui et al, 2000). It is, thus, remarkable that the chromosomal region 9p21, is potentially related to breast cancer

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

progression (Oliveira et al, 2010; Haverty et al, 2008; Silva et al, 2003; Brenner and Aldaz, 1995, Schwendel et al, 1998; Loo et al, 2008; Cairns et al, 1995).

Secondly, inactivation of *CDKN2A* gene has been shown to involve four types of genetic alterations: homozygous deletion, promoter hypermethylation, loss of heterozygosity and point mutation, of which homozygous deletion and promoter hypermethylation constitute most of the alterations (Tam et al, 2013). Further analysis has revealed that the gene is frequently homozygously lost or deleted in many tumor types, including glioma (Zadeh et al, 2007), bladder carcinoma (Abat et al, 2014), lung carcinoma (Tam et al, 2013), esophageal carcinoma (Qureshi et al, 2012), renal carcinoma (Ikuerowo et al, 2007), and breast carcinoma (Lebok et al, 2016). Hence, it is ascertained to elucidate the incidence of *CDKN2A* gene

deletion and analyze its correlation with clinicopathological parameters of breast cancer patients.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Patients:

In the present study, a total of 30 untreated histologically confirmed breast cancer patients registered at The Gujarat Cancer & Research Institute were enrolled. The study was approved by the Institute's Ethics Committee Board and general consent forms were obtained from all the patients. Detailed clinicopathological history of the patients was obtained. Histopathological details such as tumor size, lymph node status, disease stage, Bloom-Richardson score (BR score),

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

histological grade and status of ER, PR, Her2 were evaluated and reported on routine basis by the pathologists of our institute. The clinicopathological characteristics of the enrolled patients are enlisted in Table 1. All breast cancer patients in the present study were of Invasive Ductal Carcinoma (IDC) type.

Fluorescence *in-situ* Hybridization (FISH)

For detection of 9p21 deletions, FISH analysis was carried out on formalin fixed paraffin-embedded tumor tissue blocks of the enrolled breast cancer patients using commercially available ZytoLight FISH Tissue Implementation pretreatment kit. The tumor tissue sections were then deparaffinized, dehydrated with alcohol series (100%, 90%, 70%), incubated in pre-warmed heat pretreatment solution (PT1) at 90° C. Thereafter drop wise Pepsin Solution (ES1) was applied to the tissue section and incubated for 18 min

at 37 °C in a humidified chamber followed by washes in Wash Buffer (WB1). Subsequently, appropriate amount of Locus specific identifier (LSI P16 Spectrum Red/centromeric enumeration probe (CEP) 9 green dual color probe (CytoCell P16 CDKN2A) was applied. The tissue sections were incubated at 75°C for 12 min to carry out denaturation and then at 37°C for overnight hybridization in the humidified chamber. Post-hybridization washes were carried out next day in 1X Wash Buffer and dehydrated with alcohol series, followed by counterstaining with DAPI. The slides scanning and capturing was done using OLYMPUS BX61 fluorescent microscope (OLYMPUS BX61, Japan) at a magnification of 100X. Total 20 randomly selected invasive tumor cells were evaluated for interpretation. The specimens having 2 orange and 2 green signals (2O2G) were considered to have normal intact *CDKN2A* gene. Loss of one orange signal resulting in 1O2G pattern were regarded as homozygous deletion of *CDKN2A*

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

while specimens having only 2 green signals (2G) were categorized as hemizygous *CDKN2A* deletion.

Statistical analysis:

The statistical evaluation of the data was carried out using SPSS Inc. version 16 software. Two-tailed chi square test and spearman's correlation method was used to correlate the *CDKN2A* gene expression with various clinicopathological characteristics of breast cancer patients. $P \leq 0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant.

RESULTS

Clinicopathological parameters of Breast Cancer patients

As shown in Table 1, breast cancer patients enrolled in the study were in the age group of 21 to 71 years and the median age of patients was 44 years. Median age was used as a cut off to categorize the patients into younger (≤ 44) and older age group (> 44). Accordingly, 17 (57%) patients were in younger age group and 13 (43%) patients were in older age group. Among all 30 patients of breast cancer, 26 (87%) were females and 4 (13%) were males. For lymph node status, in 15 patients (50%) there were no sign of it, while lymph node was involved with tumor cells in 15 patients (50%). BR score was used to divide the patients into groups having grade 1 tumors (well-differentiated), grade 2 tumors (moderately differentiated) and grade 3 tumors (poorly differentiated). Accordingly, 9 patients (40.9%) were having grade 2 tumors

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

and 13 patients (59.1%) had grade 3 tumors. BR score data was not available for the rest 8 patients. In addition, vascular permeation was absent in 16 patients (53%), and observed in 14 patients (47%). Perineural invasion was absent in 24 patients (80%) but observed in 6 patients (20%) and perinodal extension was absent in 18 patients (60%), whereas seen in 12 patients (40%). Eleven

patients (37%) were ER and PR negative, and 19 patients (3%) were ER and PR positive. Of total patients, none patient was Her2 negative, whereas 28 patients (90.35%) were Her2 equivocal and 2 (6.7%) patients were Her2 positive. Further, 1 patient (3.3%) was in stage I, 6 patients (20%) had stage II and 11 patients (36.6%) were with stage III breast cancer.

Table: 1 - Clinicopathological parameters of Breast Cancer patients

Variables	No. of patients	(%)
Age Range	21 - 71 years	

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

Age (years)	≤44	17	57%
	>44	13	43%
Gender	Male	4	13%
	Female	26	87%
Lymph node status	Absent	15	50%
	Present	15	50%
BR Score*	3 to 5 (grade 1)	None	----
	6 to 7 (grade 2)	9	41%

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

	8 to 9 (grade 3)	13	59%
Vascular permeation	Absent	16	53%
	Present	14	47%
PNI status	Absent	24	80%
	Present	6	20%
PNE status	Absent	18	60%
	Present	12	40%
ER	Negative	9	30%

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

	Positive	21	70%
PR	Negative	9	30%
	Positive	21	70%
Her2	Negative	0	00
	Equivocal	28	93%
	Positive	2	7%
STAGE	Stage I	1	3%
	Stage II	6	20%

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

	Stage III	11	37%
	Unknown	12	40%

*BR score data was not available for 8 breast cancer patients

CDKN2A gene status by FISH:

In total breast cancer patients, *CDKN2A* gene was found to be deleted in 73% (22/30) patients, whereas 27% (8/30) had intact

CDKN2A gene. Moreover, of the total patients found to have *CDKN2A* gene deletion, 77% (17/30) patients were found to have hemizygous deletion and 23% (5/30) patients had homozygous deletion (Table 2). Representative images are shown in Figure 1.

Table 2: FISH result for *CDKN2A* gene status

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

Malignancy	Gene status		
	Normal N (%)	Deleted N (%)	
Breast Cancer	8 (27%)	22 (73%)	Hemi – 17 (57%)
			Homo – 5 (16%)

Correlation of *CDKN2A* FISH results with clinicopathological parameters in Breast Cancer

As depicted in Table 3, correlation of *CDKN2A* gene status with clinicopathological parameters of breast cancer patients was studied. It was revealed that deletion of

CDKN2A gene was significantly associated with grade 2 (moderately differentiated) breast tumors (p=0.02) as compared to grade 3 tumors (poorly differentiated). Moreover, incidence of *CDKN2A* gene deletion was significantly higher in patients without vascular permeation (p=0.04), perineural invasion (p=0.01) and perinodal extension (p=0.03) as compared to those having vascular permeation, perineural invasion

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

and perinodal extension, respectively. However, no other significant associations were observed between *CDKN2A* gene deletion and rest of the studied parameters.

Table: 3 Correlation of *CDKN2A* gene with clinicopathological parameters in Breast Cancer

Variables	<i>CDKN2A</i> gene status			χ^2	r	P
	N (%)	Normal	Deleted			
		N (%)	N (%)			
	30 (100)	8 (27)	22 (73)			
Age (years)						
≤ 44years	17 (57)	3 (18)	14 (82)	2.3	-0.27	0.13

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

> 44 years	13 (43)	5 (39)	8 (61)			
Gender						
Male	4 (13)	1(25)	3(75)	1.04	0.09	0.6
Female	26 (86)	7 (26)	19 (64)			
Lymph Node Status						
Absent	15 (50)	3 (21)	10 (79)	2.35	-0.25	0.17
Present	15 (50)	5 (33)	10 (67)			
Stage						
Stage I	1 (3)	0 (00)	1 (100)			

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

Stage II	5 (17)	2 (40)	3 (60)	10.7	0.33	0.16
Stage III	12 (40)	3 (25)	9 (75)			
BR Score						
6 to 7 (Grade 2)	9 (41)	1 (11)	8(89)	5.8	-.47	0.02
8 to 9 (Grade 3)	13 (59)	5 (38)	8 (62)			
Vascular Permeation						
Absent	16 (53)	2 (12)	14 (88)	4.2	-3.7	0.04
Present	14 (47)	6 (43)	8 (58)			
Perineural Invasion						

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

Absent	24 (80)	4 (17)	20 (83)	6.47	-.43	0.01
Present	6 (20)	4 (66)	2 (33)			
Perinodal Extension						
Absent	18 (60)	2 (12)	16 (88)	5.7	-.39	0.03
Present	12 (40)	6 (50)	6 (50)			
ER Status						
Negative	9 (30)	4 (45)	5 (55)	1.6	-.205	0.29
Positive	21 (70)	4 (19)	17 (81)			
PR Status						

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

Negative	9 (30)	4 (45)	5 (55)	3.07	-08	0.6
Positive	21 (70)	4 (19)	17 (81)			
Her2 status						
Negative	-----	-----	-----	1.6	0.04	0.8
Equivocal	28 (93)	8 (29)	20 (71)			
Positive	2 (7)	00(0)	2 (11)			

Figure-1: Representative images for signal patterns observed in FISH assay

(a) Normal pattern of *CDKN2A* gene (b) Hemizygous deletion of *CDKN2A* gene (c) Homozygous deletion of *CDKN2A* gene

DISCUSSION

CDKN2A is established as a tumor suppressor gene that encodes a specific inhibitor of cyclin-dependent kinase (CDK) 4 and 6, critical for cell cycle regulation. It plays a pivotal role in tumor suppressor networks through inducing cellular senescence that acts as a barrier to cellular transformation by oncogenic signals (Kotake et al. 2015). P16 protein encoded by *CDKN2A* has been implicated in processes such as apoptosis, cell invasion and angiogenesis. However, *CDKN2A* gene is found altered in a wide range of human cancers with loss of p16 in many malignant disorders, although overexpression of p16 is demonstrated in some tumors (Romagosa et al, 2011). Additionally, the loss of p16 may be an early event in cancer progression, because deletion of at least one copy is quite high in some

pre-malignant lesions (Liggett et al, 1998). Allelic losses of 9p21 are detected and conflicting data exist whether these changes develop early or late in the malignant progression (Gonzalez et al, 1997). Therefore, the present study aimed to detect the *CDKN2A* gene deletion in breast cancer patients.

A total of 30 breast cancer patients who underwent surgery at The Gujarat Cancer and Research Institute were included. *CDKN2A* gene was found to be deleted in 73% (22/30) and was intact in 27% (8/30) of breast cancer patients with hemizygous deletion found in 57% (17/30) and homozygous deletion in 16% (5/30) of total patients. In a study by Aftab et al (2018) entire gene deletions were observed in approximately 42.8% of breast cancers. There

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

are still other earlier studies which have reported 9p deletions in 6–25% breast cancers by array CGH (Haverty et al, 2008; Jong et al, 2004; Seute et al, 2001). Moreover, higher rates of 41% of 9p deletions were found in metastatic breast cancers or in studies employing less quantitative loss of heterozygosity (de Oliveira et al, 2010; 13, Silva et al, 2003; Brenner & Aldaz, 1995; Cairns et al, 1995. However, Lebok et al (2016) analysed 2,197 breast cancers and found 9p21 deletions in 15.3% interpretable breast tumors by FISH. The deletions observed by Lebok et al (2016) were 13.6% heterozygous and 1.7% homozygous deletions.

In addition, *CDKN2A* gene deletion has been reported in other malignancies too. Jacobsen et al (2020) observed the gene deletion in 32.1% adenocarcinoma (EAC) and 33.5%

squamous cell carcinoma (SSC) esophageal cancer patients by IHC and FISH. Also, Kotzev and Kamenova (2017) detected loss of *CDKN2A* gene in 69% esophageal adenocarcinoma specimens by FISH, including hemizygous deletion occurring with highest frequency in 54% EAC specimens whereas homozygous deletion presented in 15% EAC specimens. This is similar to the incidence of *CDKN2A* gene deletion observed in the present study. Fahmy et al (2004) too has found noticeable loss of the 9p21 signals in 90% of analyzed EAC samples by FISH. Also, in gastric cancer, *CDKN2A* deletions were found in 38.9% of the tested specimens (Qiao et al, 2021), while in 59% of non-small cell lung tumors making it the most frequent mechanism of inactivation (Tam et al, 2013).

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

Next, the correlation of *CDKN2A* gene status with the clinicopathological parameters of breast cancer patients revealed significant inverse association of *CDKN2A* gene deletion with tumor grade, vascular permeation, perineural invasion and perinodal extension. Contradictorily, Lebok et al observed that 9p21 deletion was linked to adverse tumor features, including high-grade ($p < 0.0001$) and nodal positive cancers ($p = 0.0063$), high cell proliferation ($p < 0.0001$), negative hormone receptor (ER/PR) status ($p \leq 0.0006$), and HER2 amplification ($p = 0.0078$) in breast cancer patients (Lebok et al, 2016). On the other side, Jacobsen et al (2020) did not find any correlation of *CDKN2A* gene deletion with the clinicopathological parameters of esophageal cancer patients, but the study revealed correlation of p16 protein expression with low tumor stage and better overall survival. Further, Malerova et.al. (2020) studied the significance of p16 protein expression in relation to

clinicopathological parameters and prognosis in patients with oral squamous cell carcinomas and observed that P16 positivity seems to be a negative prognostic factor in oral carcinomas. This is in line with the results obtained in the present study, showing that the *CDKN2A* gene deletion is associated with good prognostic factors.

A probable reason for the conflicting results of *CDKN2A* gene deletion could be that there are variants of the gene present due to single nucleotide polymorphism which predisposes to malignant transformation (Dębniak et al, 2005). Thus presence of different variants might lead to distinct associations with the clinicopathological parameters. The present study has observed significant associations of *CDKN2A* gene deletion with good prognosticators, indicating that the gene

International Journal of Biological Sciences and Technology (2022), Volume 13, Issue 1, Page(s): 1-27

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

deletion could be an early event in carcinogenesis. This is supported by the previous studies showing that alterations of p16 occur early during tumorigenesis as they are commonly seen in Barrett's dysplasia and peritumoral mucosa (Jacobsen et al, 2020). Moreover, Dębniak et al (2005) has suggested *CDKN2A* to be a low penetrance breast cancer susceptibility gene in Poland (Dębniak et al, 2005). Hence, on the basis of previous studies and present study result, P16 overexpression - but not expression loss was linked to adverse tumor parameters (Lebok et al, 2016). Moreover, FISH technique is considered the gold standard for gene copy number analysis. This is because it allows for precise gene copy number determination in individual cells rendering it independent of cancer tissue purity or aneuploidy.

CONCLUSION:

Although *CDKN2A* gene is well-known for its role as a tumor suppressor gene, the present study observed that the gene deletion was associated with absence of known worse prognosticators indicating that the gene expression and not loss was linked to adverse tumor parameters. Moreover, since *CDKN2A* gene deletion is considered as an early event in carcinogenesis, the association with good prognostic factors suggests the same. Hence, detection of *CDKN2A* gene deletion could help to stratify the specific subsets of patients into high risk and low risk groups. Secondly, FISH technique allows for precise gene copy number determination in individual cells, rendering it independent from the purity of cancer tissues or presence of aneusomy. FISH is thus considered the gold standard for gene copy number analysis.

References:

- Abat, D., Demirhan, O., Inandiklioglu, N., Tunc, E., Erdogan, S., Tastemir, D., Uslu IN & Tansug, Z. (2014). Genetic alterations of chromosomes, p53 and p16 genes in low-and high-grade bladder cancer. *Oncology letters*, 8(1), 25-32.
- Aftab, A., Shahzad, S., Hussain, H. M. J., Khan, R., Irum, S., & Tabassum, S. (2019). CDKN2A/P16INK4A variants association with breast cancer and their in-silico analysis. *Breast Cancer*, 26(1), 11-28.
- Brenner, A. J., & Aldaz, C. M. (1995). Chromosome 9p allelic loss and p16/CDKN2 in breast cancer and evidence of p16 inactivation in immortal breast epithelial cells. *Cancer research*, 55(13), 2892-2895.
- Cairns P, Polascik TJ, Eby Y, Tokino K, Califano J, Merlo A, Mao L, Herath J, Jenkins R, Westra W, et al. (1995). Frequency of homozygous deletion at p16/CDKN2 in primary human tumours. *Nat Gen*. 11:210–212.
- Dębniak, T., Gorski, B., Huzarski, T., Byrski, T., Cybulski, C., Mackiewicz, A., ... & Lubinski, J. (2005). A common variant of CDKN2A (p16) predisposes to breast cancer. *Journal of medical genetics*, 42(10), 763-765.
- Fahmy M, Skacel M, Gramlich TL, et al. (2004). Chromosomal gains and genomic loss of p53 and p16 genes in Barrett's esophagus detected by fluorescence in situ hybridization of cytology specimens. *Mod Pathol*, 17: 588-596.
- Gonzalez, M. V., Artimez, M. L., Rodrigo, L., López-Larrea, C., Menendez, M. J., Alvarez, V., ... & Coto, E. (1997). Mutation analysis of the p53, APC, and p16 genes in the Barrett's oesophagus, dysplasia, and adenocarcinoma. *Journal of clinical pathology*, 50(3), 212-217.
- Haverty PM, Fridlyand J, Li L, Getz G, Beroukhi R, Lohr S, Wu TD, Cavet G, Zhang Z, Chant J (2008). High-resolution genomic and expression analyses of copy number alterations in breast tumors. *Gene Chromosomes Cancer*, 47: 530–542.

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

Hui R, Macmillan RD, Kenny FS, Musgrove EA, Blamey RW, Nicholson RI, Robertson JF, Sutherland RL (2000). INK4a gene expression and methylation in primary breast cancer: overexpression of p16INK4a messenger RNA is a marker of poor prognosis. *Clin Cancer Res.* 6: 2777–2787.

Haverty PM, Fridlyand J, Li L, Getz G, Beroukhi R, Lohr S, Wu TD, Cavet G, Zhang Z, Chant J (2008). High-resolution genomic and expression analyses of copy number alterations in breast tumors. *Gene Chromosomes Cancer*, 47:530–542.

Ikuerowo, S. O., Kuczyk, M. A., von Wasielewski, R., Shittu, O. B., Jonas, U., Machtens, S., & Serth, J. (2007). p16INK4a expression and clinicopathologic parameters in renal cell carcinoma. *European urology*, 51(3), 732-738.

Jacobsen, F., Kohsar, J., Gebauer, F., Kluth, M., Hübner, C., Simon, R., ... & Melling, N. (2020). Loss of p16 and high Ki67 labeling index is associated with

poor outcome in esophageal carcinoma. *Oncotarget*, 11(12), 1007.

Jong YJ, Li LH, Tsou MH, Chen YJ, Cheng SH, Wang-Wuu S, Tsai SF, Chen CM, Huang AT, Hsu MT, Lin CH (2004). Chromosomal comparative genomic hybridization abnormalities in early- and late-onset human breast cancers: correlation with disease progression and TP53 mutations. *Cancer Genet Cytogene*, 148: 55–65

Karray-Chouayekh S, Baccouche S, Khabir A, Sellami-Boudawara T, Daoud J, Frikha M, Jlidi R, Gargouri A, Mokdad-Gargouri R (2011). Prognostic significance of p16INK4a/ p53 in Tunisian patients with breast carcinoma. *Acta histochemica* 113:508–513.

Kotake, Naemura M, Murasaki C, Inoue Y and Okamoto H (2015). Review transcriptional regulation of the p16 tumor suppressor gene department of biological and environmental chemistry. *Anticancer Research* 35: 4397-4402

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

- Kotzev, A., & Kamenova, M. (2017). Loss of P16 in Esophageal Adenocarcinoma Detected by Fluorescence in situ Hybridization and Immunohistochemistry. *Acta Medica Bulgarica*, 44(2), 14-19.
- Lebok, P., Roming, M., Kluth, M., Koop, C., Özden, C., Taskin, B., Hussein K, Lebeau A, Witzel I, Wölber L, Geist S, Paluchowski P, Wilke C, Heilenkötter U, Müller V, Schmalfeldt B, Simon R, Sauter G, Terracciano L, Krech RH, Assen A & Burandt, E. (2016). p16 overexpression and 9p21 deletion are linked to unfavorable tumor phenotype in breast cancer. *Oncotarget*, 7(49), 81322.
- Li J, Poi MJ, Tsai MD (2011). Regulatory mechanisms of tumor suppressor P16 (INK4A) and their relevance to cancer. *Biochemistry*, 50: 5566–5582.
- Liggett WH Jr, Sidransky D (1998). Role of the p16 tumor suppressor gene in cancer. *J Clin Oncol*. 16(3): 1197-206.
- Loo LW, Ton C, Wang YW, Grove DI, Bouzek H, Vartanian N, Lin MG, Yuan X, Lawton TL, Daling JR, Malone KE, Li CI, Hsu L, et al. (2008). Differential patterns of allelic loss in estrogen receptor-positive infiltrating lobular and ductal breast cancer. *Gene Chromosomes Cancer* 47:1049–1066.
- Maléřová S, Kalfeřt D, Ğrega M, Tachezy R, Klozar J (2020). The significance of p16 protein expression in oral squamous cell carcinoma. *Epidemiol Mikrobiol Imunol. Spring*; 69(2): 64-72
- Milde-Langosch K, Bamberger AM, Rieck G, Kelp B, Loning T (2001). Overexpression of the p16 cell cycle inhibitor in breast cancer is associated with a more malignant phenotype. *Breast Cancer Res Treat.* 67:61–70.
- de Oliveira, S. F. V., Oliveira, M. M. C., Urban, C. A., de Lima, R. S., Cavalli, I. J., & Ribeiro, E. M. D. S. F. (2010). Lack of association between LOH in the 9p region and clinicopathologic parameters in primary breast cancer. *Cancer genetics and cytogenetics*, 200(1), 23-27.

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

- Qiao, J., Tian, Y., Cheng, X., Liu, Z., Zhou, J., Gu, L., ... & Deng, D. (2021). CDKN2A Deletion Leading to Hematogenous Metastasis of Human Gastric Carcinoma. *Frontiers in oncology*, 5480.
- Qureshi, M. A., Jan, N., Dar, N. A., Hussain, M., & Andrabi, K. I. (2012). A novel p16INK4A mutation associated with esophageal squamous cell carcinoma in a high risk population. *Biomarkers*, 17(6), 552-556.
- Romagosa C, Simonetti S, Lopez-Vicente L, Mazo A, Leonart ME, Castellvi J, Ramon y Cajal S (2011). p16(Ink4a) overexpression in cancer: a tumor suppressor gene associated with senescence and high-grade tumors. *Oncogene*, 30: 2087–2097.
- Schwendel A, Richard F, Langreck H, Kaufmann O, Lage H, Winzer KJ, Petersen I, Dietel M (1998). Chromosome alterations in breast carcinomas: frequent involvement of DNA losses including chromosomes 4q and 21q. *Br J Canc*. 78:806–811.
- Seute A, Sinn HP, Schlenk RF, Emig R, Wallwiener D, Grischke EM, Hohaus S, Dohner H, Haas R, Bentz M (2001). Clinical relevance of genomic aberrations in homogeneously treated high-risk stage II/III breast cancer patients. *Int J Cancer*. 2001; 93:80–84.
- Sherr CJ, Roberts JM (2004). Living with or without cyclins and cyclin-dependent kinases. *Genes Dev*, 18: 2699–2711.
- Silva J, Silva JM, Dominguez G, Garcia JM, Cantos B, Rodriguez R, Larrondo FJ, Provencio M, Espana P, Bonilla F. (2003). Concomitant expression of p16INK4a and p14ARF in primary breast cancer and analysis of inactivation mechanisms. *J Pathol*. 199:289–297.
- Sung, H., Ferlay, J., Siegel, R. L., Laversanne, M., Soerjomataram, I., Jemal, A., & Bray, F. (2021). Global cancer statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA: a cancer journal for clinicians*, 71(3), 209-249.
- Tam, K. W., Zhang, W., Soh, J., Stastny, V., Chen, M., Sun, H., ... & Gazdar, A. (2013). DKN2A/p16

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7023338>

inactivation mechanisms and their relationship to smoke exposure and molecular features in non-small-cell lung cancer. *Journal of thoracic oncology*, 8(11), 1378-1388.

Vieira de Oliveira SF, Oliveira MM, Urban CA, de Lima RS, Cavalli IJ, Ribeiro EM (2010). Lack of association between LOH in the 9p region and clinicopathologic parameters in primary breast cancer. *Cancer Genet Cytogenet.*; 200:23–27.

Witkiewicz AK, Rivadeneira DB, Ertel A, Kline J, Hyslop T, Schwartz GF, Fortina P, Knudsen ES (2011). Association of RB/p16-pathway perturbations with DCIS recurrence: dependence on tumor versus tissue microenvironment. *The Am J Pathol.* 179:1171–1178.

Zadeh, M. D., Amini, R., Firoozray, M., & Derakhshandeh-Peykar, P. (2007). Frequent homozygous deletion of p16/CDKN2A gene in malignant gliomas of Iranian patients. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences: PJBS*, 10(23), 4246-4250.

THE GUJARAT CANCER & RESEARCH INSTITUTE
 (M. P. SHAH CANCER HOSPITAL) AHMEDABAD-380 016.
ધી ગુજરાત કેન્સર એન્ડ રિસર્ચ ઇન્સ્ટિટ્યૂટ
 (એમ.પી.શાહ કેન્સર હોસ્પિટલ) ન્યૂ સિવિલ હોસ્પિટલ કંપાઉન્ડ, અસારવા, અમદાવાદ-૩૮૦ ૦૧૬.

Regd. No. _____

Name : **S T I C K E R**

Age/Sex : _____

અમો નીચે સહી કરનાર (દર્દી) _____
 અને દર્દીના સગા _____ જણાવીએ છીએ કે અમોને
 ડૉક્ટરશ્રીએ બિમારી વિશે તથા તેના પરિણામોની સંપૂર્ણ માહિતી આપેલ છે. તે સંબંધે નીચે જણાવેલ તપાસ સારવારમાંથી જે કોઈપણ જરૂરી હોય તે
 કરવાની અમો ડૉક્ટરને પરવાનગી આપીએ છીએ.

૧. નિદાન માટે જરૂરી બાયોપ્સી, એન્ડોસ્કોપી, એન્જિયોગ્રાફી, સીટી સ્કેન, સોનોગ્રાફી વગેરે માટે.
૨. કોઈપણ પ્રકારના ઓપરેશન અને તેના માટે જરૂરી એનેસ્થેશીયા માટે.
૩. કોઈપણ પ્રકારની રેડિયોથેરાપી સારવાર માટે.
૪. કેમોથેરાપી સારવાર માટે.
૫. સારવાર દરમિયાન લોહી અથવા લોહીના કમ્પોનેન્ટસ આપતી વખતે સંપૂર્ણ તકેદારી રાખવા છતાં કોઈ અનિચ્છનિય પરિણામ આવે
 તો તે પણ અમો સ્વીકારવા તૈયાર છીએ.
૬. અમો લોહીના નમુના, ટીસ્ટ્યુના નમુના તથા તપાસ કે જે ગુ.કે.સી.ઇ અથવા ગુ.કે.સો. દ્વારા ચાલતા સંશોધન કાર્ય માટે પણ આપવા
 સંમત છીએ.

દર્દીની સહી _____ દર્દીના સગાની સહી _____
 તારીખ _____ તારીખ : _____

હમ (મરીજ) _____
 ઓર (મરીજ કે રીસ્તેદાર) _____

સ્વીકાર કરતે હૈ કી બિમારી કી ચિકિત્સા એવં ઉસસે હોને વાલે સંભાવિત પરિણામ કે વિષય મેં હમેં પુરી જાનકારી વી ગઈ હૈ ઈસ સમ્બન્ધ હમ નિમ્ન
 પ્રક્રિયાઓ કે લિએ અનુમતિ દેતે હૈ ।

૧. નિદાન કે લિએ આવશ્યક પ્રક્રિયા જૈસે કિ વાયોપ્સી, એન્ડોસ્કોપી, એન્જિયોગ્રાફી, સીટી સ્કેન ઈત્યાદી
૨. કિસી પ્રકાર કી શસ્ત્રક્રિયા એવં વેહોશ કરને કી આવશ્યકતા કે લિએ.
૩. વિકિરણ ચિકિત્સા (રેડિયોથેરાપી) : બ્રાહ્મ એવં આન્તરિક (બ્રેકી થેરાપી).
૪. ઓષધો ચાર (કીમોથેરાપી) કી દવાઓ કે લિએ.
૫. સંસ્થા એવં કેન્સર સોસાયટી કે રીસર્ચ કે લિએ, રક્તપેશી, ઈત્યાદી કે સેમ્પલ યા કોઈ મી જાંચ કે લિએ
૬. મુઝે જ્ઞાન હૈ કી ચિકિત્સા કે સમય, મુઝે રક્ત અથવા રક્તપેશી કી આવશ્યકતા હો સકતી હૈ, હાલાકી ઈસમેં સમી પ્રકાર કી સાવધાની
 લી જાતી હૈ, ફિર મી કુછ દુશ્ચ પરિણામ હો સકતે હૈ જો હમેં સ્વીકાર્ય હૈ.

મરીજ કે હસ્તાક્ષર _____ મરીજ કે રીસ્તેદાર કે હસ્તાક્ષર _____
 દિનાંક : _____ દિનાંક : _____

(4)

Scanned by CamScanner